

COACHES' COMPETENCY AND HOW ATHLETES' TRUST THEIR SPORTS PERFORMANCE

OLIVER L. ESTUYE, MA-PE

Nueva Ecija High School – Senior High School
SHS Teacher III, oliverestuye1126@gmail.com
Nueva Ecija, Region 3, Philippines (3900)

Abstract: Coaching is a multifaceted calling, interactive in nature and need the knowledge of various stratagems and behaviors to justify several outlooks. Sports coaches have to be compelled to possess sensible knowledge, skills and high motivation in polishing off responsibilities to provide quality athletes. aimed to determine the extent of sport coaches' competency along with: motivation, game strategy, technique, and character-building. Hence, it also elicited evaluations of athletes' level of trusts towards their coaches. The study involved randomly selected 84 teacher-coaches and 150 student-athletes in the whole division of Nueva Ecija (for secondary level only) during the school year 2019-2020. Using Pearson-r correlation coefficient, the study revealed that the trust given by the athletes to their coaches was dependent on the event played by the player. Thus, it is strongly recommended that the schools division of the cited province may provide incentive system to the coaches to attract experienced and skilled coaches to remain in their positions.

Keywords: Trust, Motivation, Game Strategy, Technique, Character Building

Introduction

The coach is a key component in developing effective and successful athletes [1]. The coach-athlete relationship is therefore at the heart of the coaching process and it is the interactions between coaches and their athletes that generate the athletes' learning and results. The relationship between coach and athlete is therefore important to the coaching process, and the interactions of coaches and their athletes produce learning and results for athletes.

Coaching is an interactive calling that requires the understanding of different strategies and actions in order to justify different perspectives. In order to create athletes of excellence, sports coaches need to possess strong knowledge, abilities and great drive. It has been demonstrated that a coach's personality can impact its ability to create effective training program, which indicates that his players have high performance. Certainly, a skilled competent coach who provides his athletes great satisfaction may encourage them to execute their sports with confidence. This may have a major impact on athletes' performance and psychological well-being through the kind of leadership behavior epitomized by the coach [6].

Since sports coaches are essential for athlete development, there is a link between coaching skills and the performance of athletes and their achievements. A fascinating challenge in sport psychology is therefore to examine how coaching skills and capabilities are associated with performance of athletes.

The coach continuously evaluates the performance of his/her athletes, the student athletes also studies on the personality and conduct of his/her coaches. These views of coaching skills and

capabilities might influence student athletes' performance and provide significant insights into key information needed to enhance this connection [2]. It also appears acceptable, while evaluating the coaching performance, to incorporate student athlete's opinions. The concept of carrying out a comprehensive assessment which might produce an accurate profile of a particular person's performance is very essential.

Coaching competence, skills and capabilities are footing a competitive edge in any sport. It's a complex operation, which requires unique strategy and behavior to achieve outlooks [11]. These coaching competencies may be seen as the extent to which coaches believe that they will have an influence on athlete's learning and performance. Coaches must be able to standardize performance approaches and athlete strength in order to facilitate effective coordination of the team strategy with the strength and weaknesses of the opponent. [4] developed four factors about coaching competencies. It is motivation, strategy, technique and developing personality.

In line with this, the researcher, who has been a team coach in Volleyball for the last 12 years, was prompted to conduct this study. Hence, there was a little number of researches that would give emphasis on coaches' competency and the trust given by the athletes, thus, the completion of this study.

The purpose of the study was to provide answers and rationale for: (1) How can the degree of skills in the field of sport coaches be defined as: motivation; game strategy; technology and creating character as assessed by both groups of respondents? (2) How can the trainer be defined by the two groups of interviewees in terms of confidence level? And (3) Does the degree of skills of sports coaches correspond substantially to the level of confidence of athletes?

Methodology

This study employed the descriptive design of research. This method of research according to Scates and Goodwin (2007) is ideal for investigation as the study aimed to present facts concerning the nature, status, and characteristic of any kind of phenomena and related observation to the presence and absence of certain other conditions to develop a frame of relationship.

This design was chosen by the researcher because it was the most appropriate design in describing the level of competency among provincial meet coaches, the trust of players they give to their coaches in relation to their sports performance.

The research respondents on this study were junior and senior high school athletes and their coaches who represent the various events in schools' division of Nueva Ecija. These respondents were chosen using the purposive sampling procedure. This sampling procedure according to [12] uses a criterion in selecting the samples. The researcher confined his study to players and coaches who qualified for the provincial meet.

Table 1. *Summary table on the respondents of the study.*

Congressional Districts	Events	Coaches n1	Players n2	Total nt	%
Congressional District I	Individual	7	7	14	5.98
	Dual	2	4	6	2.56
	Team	6	20	26	11.11
Congressional District II	Individual	3	3	6	2.56
	Dual	4	9	13	5.56
	Team	8	24	32	13.68
Congressional District III	Individual	8	8	16	6.84
	Dual	3	3	6	2.56

	Team	7	19	26	11.11
Congressional District IV	Individual	7	19	26	11.11
	Dual	18	31	49	20.94
	Team	18	31	49	20.94
<i>Total</i>		<i>84</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>234</i>	<i>100.00</i>

The researcher prepared a letter of request addressed to the Public-School District Supervisors for the conduct of the study. Upon obtaining the approval of the said request, the researcher personally went to the schools of the respondents to administer the questionnaires. He set an appointment with the identified respondents to ensure that he was entertained by the respondents during their available time to accomplish the questionnaires.

The questionnaires were reinforced by unstructured interviews which was conducted among the respondents. The questionnaire dealt with a survey on the level of competency of coaches and the trust given by the players to their coaches

Table 2. *Scoring used in the evaluation of the questionnaire through 4-point Likert scaling.*

Value	Range	Descriptions	Interpretations
4	3.25-4.00	Very Great Extent	Very High Competency
3	2.50-3.24	Great Extent	High Competency
2	1.75-2.49	Less Extent	Low Competency
1	1.00-1.74	To no Extent	Very Low Competency

The questionnaire was subjected to validation because it was formulated personally by the researcher with the help of his adviser. A draft of this was tried out among 10 players in the division of Nueva Ecija who were not be included in the study. The try out phase was personally conducted by the researcher to solicit feedback as to the complexity of the items answered. The comments and suggestions given by these respondents were the bases in revising the final questionnaire.

The instrument underwent reliability test, using test-retest method. The dry run was done twice to the same set of respondents.

After its first administration the researcher re-administered the same questionnaire after a week days. The results from the two dry runs were recorded and statistically treated to establish the reliability. The questionnaire obtained a reliability index of 0.9345, qualitatively describes as excellent test.

Another source of data used in this study were the unstructured interviews among some of the respondents during the distribution of the questionnaire by the researcher. These were done to validate and substantiate the responses they gave in the questions/items posed in the questionnaire.

The researcher made use of the following statistical tools such as the weighted mean and correlation coefficient. To interpret and analyze the data on the competency and trust by coaches and players, the weighted mean was used. In establishing significant relationship between the profile variables of the coaches and their competency, correlation coefficient was used.

Results and Discussions

After computing for the corresponding statistical treatments of data, the subsequent tables are presented to bring light to the main objectives of the study. Table 3 shows the evaluations of the two sets of respondents on the coaches' level of competency based on the indicated sub-components for it.

Table 3. *Analysis on the coaches' competency based on the evaluations by the coaches and athletes.*

Coaches' Competency	Coaches		Athletes	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Motivation	3.76	Very High Competency	3.72	Very High Competency
2. Game Strategy	3.73	Very High Competency	3.71	Very High Competency
3. Technique	3.72	Very High Competency	3.36	Very High Competency
4. Character Building	3.71	Very High Competency	3.19	High Competency
<i>General Mean (GWM)</i>	<i>Weighted</i> 3.75	<i>Very High Competency</i>	3.44	<i>Very High Competency</i>

In general, the rated competency level of the coaches based on their self-evaluation is computed at 3.75 (very high competency), slightly higher than the rates given by the student-athletes slated at 3.44 (very high competency). This means that the teacher-coaches of the four (4) congressional districts of Nueva Ecija for high school level have displayed a very high competency of their coaching skills which were evaluated along their competency on: motivation; game strategy; technique; and character building.

Sport coaches are essential in sustaining the performance of a team and its sport athletes as mentioned by [3]. Coaches follow a range of established strategies in order to build and maintain a high quality of athletic skill and communication in the team according to the National Association for Sports and Physical Education.

It was also underlined that, despite their exceptional performance, the team may suffer from bad strategies on the field. One tangible approach to achieve it is to partition the team in half and simulate contests which oppose one half of the team. The workouts should also be organized around routines that encourage team-building. To get the most of this approach, activities and exercises should be done that keep these people near. To improve Team performance is important to working together and understanding when and how to depend upon the abilities of each other.

Table 4 displays the evaluations of the two sets of respondents on the athletes' trust towards their coaches, which was evaluated through a 22-item questionnaire checklist.

Table 4. *Analysis on the level of trust given to coaches based on the evaluations of the two sets of respondents.*

Respondents' Category	Mean	Description
Coaches	3.90	Very Great Extent
Athletes	3.76	Very Great Extent

As manifested in table 4, both sets of respondents gave a very high rates for the athletes' trust towards the coaches – with 3.90 (very great extent) for the teacher-coaches; and 3.76 (very great extent) for the student-athletes. The finding denotes that the student-athletes gave a very high respect and conviction towards their coaches – especially during the onset of trainings for the athletes (*as facilitated and designed by the coaches*). Hence, the teacher-coaches also gave a very high self-regard in terms of their sports performance – focusing on their coaching skills.

The athletes need the coach's capacity to develop them as individuals, according to [8]. According to the analysis. The sports environment frequently lays enormous demands on athletes in physically and psychologically. They have reservations about their skills and can compete harshly physically. Thus, players must "trust" their coach to provide technical/physical direction and psychological support if they don't. They must be present to help them achieve.

Table 5 encapsulates data on the relationships between coaches' competency and athletes' trust.

Table 5. *Analysis on the relationship of coaches' competency and athletes' trust.*

Indicators on Coaches' Competency	r-value	p-value	Decision
Motivation	0.1804	0.0084*	Significant
Game Strategy	0.1640	0.0420*	Significant
Technique	0.1674	0.0378*	Significant
Character Building	0.1597	0.0479*	Significant
<i>Overall Coaches Competency</i>	<i>0.1681</i>	<i>0.0361*</i>	<i>Significant</i>

*df is 1,60. A p-value with * is significant at 0.05.*

Significantly, all indicators of the coaches' competency were notably linked to the athletes' trust towards the performance of their coaches. All p-values in the said evaluations were below the significant level of 0.05, thus negating the assumption of the null hypothesis. It can be deduced then, that each component of the coaches' competency (and the overall construct) is significantly intertwined on the trust bestowed to them by their student-athletes and vice versa.

[7] confirmed this finding, stating that women had a better insight into and sensitivity than men's sentiments. This shows that people in general feel that gender differentials exist; thus, women as a group have a certain innate ability/skill that makes them more empathetic than males.

However, they claimed that this occurs only if the role of gender is outstanding. As such, this view would be predicted to be less dominant in circumstances when the gender role is broken (female coach works alongside a man).

In sport, coaches have a crucial role to play, according to [10], by closely working together with athletes to enhance their physical, technological and psychological skills via the use of their own experience and know-how. The job of the coach is for an athlete to attain greater performance levels, which may not be achieved otherwise by the athlete. However, the coach's knowledge and know-how is not the only key in athlete's success. One contributory factor to this is the coach's long years of experience in the sport he coaches.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The following conclusions were drawn, based on the important findings of the study:

1. Coaches from the New Ecija Division exhibited certain competency level in coaching their players via motivation, game strategy, technique and character building. They also have efficient strategies applied in sport training.

2. The players put their maximum trust to their coaches for these players to imbibe and instill in them the skills and competence provided to them by their coaches.

3. The trust given by the players to their coaches is dependent on the event played by the player. There are events which require the players to fully rely on their own individual capabilities in order to win.

Thus, the following actions are strongly recommended: (1) The Athletic and Sports Unit of the division of Nueva Ecija should establish standards in the selection of sports coaches (similar to the ranking procedure) to ensure that coaches with high competency may be chosen to train players. This is to ensure the nurturance of competent players. Thus, we strongly propose the following actions: (1) In order to guarantee that coaches with high competence are elected to teach athletes, the Athletic and Sports unit of the Nueva Ecija division should put out requirements for the selection of sports coaches, comparable to the ranking process. This is to guarantee that the appropriate players are nurtured. This is done in order to enhance the confidence of sportswomen in their trainers by increasing their good behavior towards sports. Hence, the Athletic and Sports Unit of the division should incorporate and give prime importance to the development of players' trust to their coaches in their trainings aside from the skills training they provide. A regular discussion on this may be given before any other skills training is done. (2) The division may provide incentive system to coaches so as to attract experienced coaches remain in their positions. Aside from the financial benefits, they may be given awards and recognition which they may use for their promotion in the future. and (3) MAPEH Teachers should intentionally incorporate in their lessons the value of trust so that prospective athletes may readily be equipped with this value and use this during sports competition.

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